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PII: S2949-7361(26)00084-9
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2026.100418>
Reference: GRETS 100418

To appear in: *Green Technologies and Sustainability*

Received date: 22 February 2026

Revised date: 14 May 2026

Accepted date: 17 May 2026

Please cite this article as: K. Bouamri, H. Oukfi, I. Zouitane et al., Comparative study of functional activities and microorganism's communities in agro-ecological and conventional soil of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) crops, *Green Technologies and Sustainability* (2026), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2026.100418>.

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Comparative study of functional activities and microorganism's communities in agro-ecological and conventional soil of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) crops

Khawla Bouamri^{1*}, Hicham Oukfi¹, Ilham Zouitane¹, Mohamed Ferioun², Said Louahlia³, Rachid Bouamri⁴, Khalid Derraz⁵, Saad Ibsouda Koraichi¹, Naïma El Ghachtouli¹.

¹ Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology and Bioactive Molecules, Sciences and Technology Faculty, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco

² Multidisciplinary Laboratory of Exact and Applied Sciences (LPSEA), Higher School of Technology Fkih Ben Salah, Sultan Moulay Slimane University, Beni Mellal, Morocco

³ Laboratory of Integrative Plant Biology and Biotechnology (BEAS), Faculty of Sciences Dhar El Mahraz, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco

⁴ Department of Environment and Plant Protection, National School of Agriculture of Meknes, Meknes, Morocco

⁵ Laboratory of Functional Ecology and Environment, Sciences and Technology Faculty, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco.

*Corresponding author: Naïma El Ghachtouli: naima.elghachtouli@usmba.ac.ma

Address: Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology and Bioactive Molecules, Faculty of Science and Technology, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Route Immouzer, P. O. Box 2202, Fez, Morocco

E-mail address: naima.elghachtouli@usmba.ac.ma

Phone: +(212) 655559261.

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9
10 6 ¹ Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology and Bioactive Molecules, Sciences and Technology Faculty, Sidi
11 7 Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco

12 8 ² Multidisciplinary Laboratory of Exact and Applied Sciences (LPSEA), Higher School of Technology Fkih Ben
13 9 Salah, Sultan Moulay Slimane University, Beni Mellal, Morocco

14 10 ³ Laboratory of Integrative Plant Biology and Biotechnology (BEAS), Faculty of Sciences, Dhar El Mahraz, Sidi
15 11 Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco

16 12 ⁴ Department of Environment and Plant Protection, National School of Agriculture of Meknes, Meknes, Morocco

17 13 ⁵ Laboratory of Functional Ecology and Environment, Sciences and Technology Faculty, Sidi Mohamed Ben
18 14 Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco.

19 15 *Corresponding author: El Ghachtouli Naïma: naima.elghachtouli@usmba.ac.ma

20 16 Address: Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology and Bioactive Molecules, Faculty of Science and
21 17 Technology, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Route Immouzer, P. O. Box 2202, Fez, Morocco

22 18 E-mail address: naima.elghachtouli@usmba.ac.ma

23 19 Phone: +(212) 655559261.

24 20 ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5452-5406>

25 21
26 22 **Abstract:**

27 23 Land management practices are widely known to influence soil quality. In this ecosystem, soil
28 24 microorganisms participate in soil biogeochemical cycles; in particular, the transformation of
29 25 organic matter is essential for plant nutrition. This study aimed to assess differences in the
30 26 functional diversity and structure of soil microbial communities between two tomato plant
31 27 cultures in Morocco: one with conventional management and the other with agroecological
32 28 practices. The soil functional diversity was assessed by evaluating the microbial metabolic
33 29 capabilities using the Biolog EcoPlate™ microplate method and measuring soil enzyme
34 30 activities. The microbial biomass of bacteria, actinomycetes, and fungi was evaluated by
35 31 medium-based cultures. The analysis demonstrated that the soil microbial community reacts
36 32 differently depending on the mode of management. Results showed that the organic farming
37 33 soil exhibited significantly higher metabolic activity and diversity, as indicated by the average
38 34 well color development (AWCD) value of 0.79 compared to 0.61 in the conventional soil.
39 35 Similarly, the soil activities of β -D-galactosidase, phosphatase, and urease were markedly

36 greater in the organic soil. Moreover, the microbial populations of bacteria, actinomycetes, and
37 fungi were more abundant in the organic soil. These findings demonstrate the positive impact
38 of organic farming practices on sustaining long-term soil productivity and health, supporting
39 their role in enhancing sustainability and productivity in agroecosystems.

40 **Keywords:** Tomato, functional diversity, enzyme activity, soil management.

42 1 Introduction

43 Morocco is one of the leading tomato producers in the world, with an average annual production
44 of around 1.5 million tons. Tomatoes are one of the most important vegetable crops grown in
45 Morocco, accounting for over 30% of the country's total vegetable production (FAO, 2023).
46 Most tomatoes are cultivated in open fields using conventional or organic farming techniques.
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48 Conventional management is generally characterized by the intensive use of synthetic
49 fertilizers, pesticides, and irrigation inputs to maximize crop yield. In contrast, agroecological
50 practices rely on organic amendments, crop rotations, and biological processes to maintain soil
51 fertility and ecological balance while reducing external chemical inputs. As is well known, land
52 management has a significant impact on soil quality, especially the biomass and activity of
53 microorganisms, which are sensitive to the methods used in soil management (Gomez et al.,
54 2006; Liang et al., 2018). Although numerous studies have highlighted the effects of farming
55 systems on soil microbial communities, the extent to which conventional and organic
56 management differentially affect microbial functional diversity and activity in Moroccan
57 tomato-growing systems remains insufficiently explored. Addressing this gap is essential for
58 understanding how soil management practices influence soil health and sustainability in this
59 key agricultural sector (Kumar et al., 2017; B. Liu et al., 2015). In order to analyze the microbial
60 metabolic diversity in agricultural soils under various management practices, community-level
61 catabolic profiles (CLPPs) analyzed by using Biolog EcoPlates have been widely used. Based
62 on the ability of microorganisms to oxidize different carbon substrates, it has been reported to
63 be a sensitive approach to detect modifications due to soil management (Feigl et al., 2017; Liang
64 et al., 2018). The Biolog EcoPlates contain carbon sources and a tetrazolium violet redox dye
65 that turns purple if inoculated microorganisms extracted from the soil utilize these sources
66 (Gomez et al., 2006; Nagata et al., 2023).

67 Numerous studies have been carried out in the area of functional diversity of microbial
68 communities in agricultural soils to investigate the impact of soil management techniques on
69 microbial biodiversity and related biological processes (Islam et al., 2011; Liang et al., 2018;
70 Nagata et al., 2023). A study that compared the microbial diversity of agricultural soils under
71 conventional and agroecological management practices demonstrated more efficient use of
72 carbon substrates in agroecological systems, which could counteract the negative effect of the
73 lack of synthetic fertilisation (Chavarria et al., 2018). In addition, previous studies examined
74 the impact of crop rotation on microbial diversity in agricultural soils. It was found that crop
75 rotation increases soil microbial diversity by promoting the presence of many beneficial
76 microbial species; this was linked to improved crop nutrient availability, which resulted in
77 higher yields and improved soil health (De Quadros et al., 2012; Q. Liu et al., 2023).

78 Understanding the impact of soil management practices on microbial communities is vital for
79 promoting agriculture, especially in intensive cropping systems like Moroccan tomato farming,
80 and for guiding more sustainable soil management strategies (Feigl et al., 2017). Despite the
81 availability of advanced techniques such as high-throughput pyrosequencing, next-generation
82 sequencing, and Biolog EcoPlates (Niu et al., 2023; Wolińska et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2022),
83 the functional responses of microbial communities to different fertilisation regimes remain
84 underexplored in Moroccan soils. A new and sensitive method for detecting changes caused by
85 soil management is the assessment of microbial metabolic diversity using Community-Level
86 Physiological Profiles (CLPPs) via Biolog EcoPlates (Xu et al., 2015), which offers valuable
87 insights into the functional potential and resilience of soil microbial communities under various
88 regimes. In this context, the combined use of Community-Level Physiological Profiles (CLPPs)
89 via Biolog EcoPlates and soil enzyme activity assays represents a valuable and integrative
90 approach to assess microbial functional diversity and soil biological activity. However, studies
91 jointly applying these complementary methods to compare agroecological and conventional
92 systems remain limited. Particularly, still, few studies have examined this variability within the
93 Moroccan context. Therefore, the primary objective of this study is to address this gap by
94 investigating the differences in the functional diversity and structure of microbial communities
95 in two distinct tomato-cultivated soils in Morocco, one under conventional management and
96 the other employing agroecological practices. Additionally, the microbial biomass of bacteria,
97 actinomycetes, and fungi was measured using medium-based cultures. The soil's functional
98 diversities were evaluated by assessing microbial metabolic capabilities with the Biolog
99 EcoPlate™ microplate method and by measuring soil enzyme activities. We hypothesize that

100 agroecological practices enhance microbial diversity, activity, and overall soil biological
101 functioning compared to conventional systems. The findings enhance our understanding of how
102 different management strategies impact microbial diversity and activity, providing empirical
103 support for more ecologically sound and sustainable soil management practices in tomato
104 production systems.

105 **2 Materials and methods**

106 **2.1 Soil sampling**

107 The soil samples were collected in-depth 30 cm from two tomato fields in the Agadir region
108 (south of Morocco), one managed conventionally (30°09'29.3"N 9°27'19.9" W) and the other
109 one (30°08'13.1"N 9°20'57.7"W) by using organic farming practices. To reduce the bias due to
110 variation in local soil heterogeneity and to improve representativeness. Two composite samples
111 were prepared. For each management system, five rhizosphere subsamples (100 g each) were
112 collected following a W-shaped sampling pattern across the study area to capture spatial
113 variability. These subsamples were thoroughly homogenized to obtain one composite sample
114 per system (500 g for organic soil and 500 g for conventional soil). The composite samples
115 were stored at low temperature until analysis. Subsequently, three analytical replicates were
116 performed from each composite sample to ensure the reliability of laboratory measurements.

117 **2.2 Soil physicochemical analysis**

118 The soil pH in H₂O and the electrical conductivity were measured using standardised
119 procedures NF ISO 10389 and NF ISO 11265. The percentage of carbon in the total organic
120 matter was determined based on the NF ISO 14235 method. The total amounts of available
121 nutrients, including Ca, K, Mg, P, Fe, Mn, NO₃⁻-N, and NH₄⁺-N, were quantified by ICP-AES
122 (Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometer) after digestion according to the
123 NFX31-120 and NFX31-121 standards. The total nitrogen content was measured according to
124 the NF ISO 11260 standard.

125 **2.3 Bacteria, actinomycetes, and soil-borne fungi counting**

126 The composite soil samples were used for the isolation of bacteria, actinomycetes, and soil-
127 borne fungi. For each composite sample, 10 g of soil was suspended in 90 mL of tryptone salt
128 (TS), followed by serial decimal dilutions. Bacteria, actinomycetes, and soil-borne fungi were
129 isolated using LB agar (Luria–Bertani), ATC (Actinomycete Isolation Agar), and MA (Malt
130 Agar) media, respectively.

131 **2.4 Soil enzyme activities**

132 β -D-galactosidase activity was assessed using a method based on the procedure outlined by
133 Eivazi & Tabatabai (1988), with minor modifications. 4g of fresh soil were combined with 25
134 mL of distilled water at pH 7 and agitated using a shaker at 250 rpm for 20 minutes at room
135 temperature. Then, after centrifugation (6000 g for 5 min), the supernatant was taken and
136 considered as the crude soil extract. Then, 25 μ l of p-nitrophenyl β -D-galactopyranoside was
137 added to 125 μ l of the obtained crude soil extract. The resulting mixture was then incubated at
138 37°C for 1 hour. To terminate the reaction, 25 μ l of 0.5 M CaCl₂ and 100 μ l of 0.5 M Tris buffer
139 (pH 12) were introduced. After shaking the mixture for 10 minutes, it was subsequently filtered.
140 The concentration of p-nitrophenol (PNP) in the filtrate was quantified by measuring its optical
141 density at 405 nm. As a control, a sample was prepared by adding the substrate after the
142 incubation period and just before halting the reaction.

143 The phosphatase activity was evaluated through a customized adaptation of the Tabatabai &
144 Bremner (1969) method. In this process, 4g of fresh soil was combined with 25 mL of distilled
145 water. The mixture was vigorously shaken at 250 rpm for 10 minutes. Followed by
146 centrifugation (6000 g for 5 min), the supernatant was taken and considered the crude soil
147 extract. Then, the addition of 25 μ l of 4-nitrophenyl phosphate to 125 μ l of the resulting crude
148 soil extract. Subsequently, the blend was allowed to incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes. To halt
149 the reaction, 25 μ l of 0.5 M CaCl₂ and 100 μ l of 0.5 M Tris buffer (pH 12) were introduced,
150 and the mixture was agitated for an additional 10 minutes before being filtered.

151 The quantification of p-nitrophenol (PNP) in the filtrate was carried out by measuring its optical
152 density at 405 nm. A control sample was included, where the substrate was added post the
153 incubation period, just before stopping the reaction, to ensure the reliability of the results.

154 The urease activity was assessed using the adapted method of Mulvaney (1996). In a test tube,
155 4 grams of fresh soil were weighed and mixed with 25 mL of distilled water. The medium was
156 stirred for 10 minutes at a speed of 250 rpm. The nitrogen content in the form of ammonium
157 (N-NH₄⁺) released by ureases was quantified by adding a urea solution. After incubation at
158 25°C for 3 hours, a solution of ammonium salicylate was added to the mixture. Once a blue-
159 green coloration was revealed, centrifugation was performed (5000 rpm for 5 minutes), and the
160 intensity of this coloration in the supernatant was measured using a spectrophotometer at a
161 wavelength of 650 nm.

2.5 Level Community Physiological Profiles determination – Biolog EcoPlate

163 To evaluate the catabolic potential of soil microorganisms in samples of both organic and
164 conventional soils, we utilized the Biolog EcoPlate method. Each EcoPlate is equipped with 96
165 wells, containing 31 different carbon sources, with three replicates. These carbon sources are
166 found naturally in the soil, some of which are derived from plant root exudates. Furthermore,
167 every plate incorporates a blank well filled with water (Xu et al., 2015).

168 The substrates within these wells can be categorized into five main groups: carbohydrates ($n =$
169 10), carboxylic and ketonic acids ($n = 9$), amino acids ($n = 6$), polymers ($n = 4$), and amides (n
170 $= 2$). This comprehensive approach allows us to thoroughly examine the metabolic capabilities
171 and preferences of soil microorganisms across various carbon sources, shedding light on their
172 potential roles in soil ecosystems.

173 To initiate the process, freshly collected samples of both organic (Orga) and conventional
174 (Conv) soils were obtained, with each sample weighing 1 gram. These soil samples were then
175 suspended in small bottles containing 9 mL of sterile physiological water. Subsequently, the
176 bottles were subjected to agitation for 30 minutes at 22°C and a rotation speed of 150 rpm.
177 Following a settling period of 10 minutes, 1 mL of the supernatant was diluted in 9 mL of sterile
178 physiological water. The next step involved the inoculation of the Biolog EcoPlate. This was
179 accomplished by pipetting 125 microliters of each prepared soil sample into individual wells of
180 the EcoPlate. Three replicates of each soil sample were used within the same plate to ensure the
181 reliability and robustness of the results. The plates were then placed in an incubator at 25°C for
182 240 hours, with absorbance measurements taken at 590 nm and recorded at 24-hour intervals.
183 Subsequently, for further analysis, readings at the 72-hour mark were selected as the most
184 suitable, as they represented the point of optimum optical density and provided the most
185 relevant data for our investigation.

186 For each plate, we computed the Average Well Color Development (AWCD) every 24 hours
187 using the approach outlined by Garland & Mills (1991). This involved taking the mean of the
188 optical densities (OD_{590}) from the 31 wells. Furthermore, we determined the AWCD for each
189 group of substrates at the 72-hour mark. To ensure accuracy, we adjusted the absorbance values
190 of each well by subtracting the optical density (OD_{590}) of the control well (containing water).
191 Additionally, a threshold value of $OD_{590} = 0.25$ was employed to classify substrates as
192 metabolized when their absorbance exceeded this value (Bochner et al., 2001). Based on the
193 72-hour data, we calculated the Shannon Diversity (H_0), Shannon Evenness (E), Richness (S),
194 and AWCD indexes for different substrate groups using the respective formulae (Xu et al.,
195 2015; Ferioun et al., 2025):

196 Average Well Color Development: $AWCD = \sum OD_c / 31$

197 Shannon diversity: $H' = -\sum p_i * \ln(p_i)$

198 Shannon evenness: $E = H' / \ln(S)$

199 Richness: $S = \text{Numbers of catabolized substrates (OD}_{590} \geq 0.25)$

200 Where:

201 p_i = proportional color development of the well over the total color development of all wells
202 of a plate.

203 OD_c = reading of the well OD_{590} - reading of the control well OD_{590}

204 2.6 Statistical analysis

205 For microbial counting, soil enzyme activities, and microbial diversity indexes, data were first
206 checked for normality and homogeneity of variance using appropriate diagnostic tests.
207 Subsequently, means were compared using Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test
208 at $p \leq 0.05$ following one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), performed using Minitab
209 statistical software. Results are presented as mean \pm standard error. Heatmaps were adopted to
210 illustrate the variability of the 31 substrates across different treatments. Heatmaps were
211 generated using the pheatmap package in RStudio software (R Core Team, 2018).

212 3 Results

213 3.1 Soil physicochemical properties

214 The two soil types, organic and conventional, from the rhizosphere of *Solanum lycopersicum*
215 were characterized. The main physicochemical parameters are shown in Table 1. The soil was
216 classified as sandy loam in texture. Key chemical parameters differed between the two systems.
217 The pH was slightly alkaline in both soils, with values of 8.31 (organic) and 8.60
218 (conventional). Electrical conductivity was lower in the organic soil (0.13 mS/cm) compared to
219 the conventional soil (0.22 mS/cm). Organic matter and total nitrogen contents were higher in
220 the organic soil (2.21% and 0.17%, respectively) than in the conventional soil (0.8% and
221 0.05%). Similarly, most available nutrients (Ca, K, Mg, Fe, Mn, NO_3^- -N, and NH_4^+ -N) were
222 more abundant in the organic soil, whereas phosphorus (P) was higher in the conventional soil.

223 3.2 Microbial counting

224 The microbial load present in a soil sample offers valuable insights into various aspects,
225 including microbial diversity, biological activity, and indicators of soil health, particularly in
226 relation to the effects of agricultural inputs.

227 Table 2 illustrates the Enumeration of microorganisms in both organic and conventional soil
228 samples using different culture media: Luria-Bertani (LB), TCA (Actinomycete Isolation
229 Agar), and Malt extract (MA). The results demonstrate distinct differences between the two
230 types of soil. Organic soil exhibits a significantly higher bacterial load, with counts reaching up
231 to 230 colony-forming units per gram multiplied by 10^6 (10^6 CFU g^{-1} of soil), whereas the
232 conventional soil shows a reduced bacterial load, measuring around 145.66×10^6 CFU g^{-1} of soil.
233 Furthermore, the analysis of actinobacteria, another important microbial group, reveals a
234 substantial disparity between organic and conventional soil. In organic soil, the load of
235 actinobacteria is notably higher, reaching 73.33×10^6 CFU g^{-1} of soil. On the other hand, the
236 conventional soil exhibits a significantly lower count, with less than 13.33×10^6 CFU g^{-1} of soil
237 of actinobacteria. Additionally, the investigation of fungal load provides intriguing findings.
238 Organic soil displays a significant presence of fungi, with a count of 3.6×10^6 CFU g^{-1} of soil,
239 signifying the favorable conditions for fungal growth and development. In contrast, the
240 conventional soil is nearly absent of fungal colonies, indicating potential limitations or
241 disturbances in the fungal community. These observations emphasize the significant disparities
242 in microbial populations between organic and conventional soil samples. The higher microbial
243 load, particularly in terms of bacteria, actinobacteria, and fungi, in organic soil indicates a more
244 thriving and diverse soil ecosystem, which is crucial for soil health and sustainable agricultural
245 practices.

246 3.3 Soil enzyme activities

247 Soil enzymatic activity can yield valuable insights into soil health, quality, and the
248 biogeochemical cycles taking place within it. Urease, β -galactosidase, and phosphatase were
249 chosen because they are widely recognized as sensitive indicators of soil microbial activity and
250 play key roles in essential nutrient cycling processes, particularly carbon, nitrogen, and
251 phosphorus transformations. Figure 1A showcases the measurement of urease activity in
252 conventional and organic soils, revealing a significant difference in potential urease activity
253 between the two soil types. The organic soil displayed a greater potential urease activity, with
254 a value of $43.55 \mu g \text{ N-NH}_4^+ \cdot h^{-1} \cdot g^{-1}$ DW of soil, whereas the conventional soil showed a lower
255 urease activity of $2.1 \mu g \text{ N-NH}_4^+ \cdot h^{-1} \cdot g^{-1}$ DW.

256 Regarding the activity of β -galactosidase, the organic soil exhibits a significantly high activity
257 level of $2.2 \mu\text{mole [PNP]/min/g}$ dry soil. Whereas the conventional soil shows lower activity
258 $0,09 \mu\text{mole [PNP]/min/g}$ dry soil (Figure 1B). On the other hand, the phosphatase enzymatic
259 activity in both organic and conventional soils showed significant differences, as illustrated in
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260 Figure 1C. The organic soil exhibits the highest phosphatase enzymatic activity value,
261 measuring 36.7 $\mu\text{mole [PNP]/min/g DW}$ of soil, while the conventional soil displays the lowest
262 value, measuring 3.8 $\mu\text{mole [PNP]/min/g DW}$.

264 3.4 Microbial Community Substrate Utilization Profile (CLPP)

265 The Biolog EcoPlates were used to quantitatively and qualitatively assess the physiological
266 profile of the microbial community in both types of agricultural soils. The variation of the
267 evaluated parameters according to soil type, incubation time, and substrate category is presented
268 in Figure 2. Overall, the AWCD (Average Well Color Development) increased progressively
269 over the 8-day incubation period in both soils. As shown in Figure 2, no difference in microbial
270 activity was observed during the initial 48 hours. Clear differentiation between treatments
271 emerged after 72 hours, where AWCD values reached 0.79 in the organic soil and 0.61 in the
272 conventional soil.

273 The temporal evolution of AWCD further highlights differences in substrate utilization patterns
274 between soil types (Figure 3A). Across the various carbon groups in the EcoPlate, higher
275 activity was consistently observed in the organic soil. For example, AWCD values for polymers
276 reached 1.05 in organic soil compared to 0.85 in conventional soil, while amines–amides
277 showed values of 1.06 and 0.60, respectively. In both soils, microbial communities
278 preferentially utilized polymers, amino acids, and amines–amides, whereas lower utilization
279 was observed for carbohydrates and carboxylic acids. Similarly, the dynamics of the diversity
280 indices—including evenness (E), Shannon index (S), and substrate richness (R) followed
281 comparable trends over the incubation period (Figure 3B), with consistently higher values
282 recorded in the organic soil.

283 The integration of metabolic responses at the substrate level is illustrated by the heatmap
284 (Figure 4), which reveals distinct patterns of carbon source utilization between treatments. The
285 organic soil exhibited greater consumption of several substrates, including Tween 40, Tween
286 80, pyruvic acid methyl ester, putrescine, L-phenylalanine, itaconic acid, glycyl-L-glutamic
287 acid, glycogen, glucose-1-phosphate, D, L- α -glycerol phosphate, D-mannitol, D-cellobiose, D-
288 galactonic acid- γ -lactone, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, L-arginine, and D-malic acid. In contrast, the
289 conventional soil showed relatively higher utilization of γ -hydroxybutyric acid, L-asparagine,
290 L-serine, N-acetyl-D-glucosamine, and β -methyl-D-glucose. Both soils displayed limited or no

291 utilization of certain substrates, such as i-erythritol, L-threonine, D-xylose, α -ketobutyric acid,
1 292 α -D-lactose, and 2-hydroxybenzoic acid.
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7 294 **4 Discussion**

9 295 This study aimed to assess the variations in functional diversity and soil microbial community
10 296 structure between two distinct tomato plant culture systems in Morocco: one managed
11 297 conventionally and the other using agroecological methods. The results highlight clear
12 298 differences between the two soil types. Regarding the physicochemical properties, higher pH
13 299 and electrical conductivity (EC) were observed under conventional management, whereas
14 300 lower values were recorded in soils receiving organic amendments. The reduction in pH under
15 301 organic conditions can be attributed to microbial decomposition of organic inputs, which
16 302 produces organic acids and CO₂, contributing to soil acidification (Mithlesh et al., 2019). In
17 303 contrast, the elevated EC in conventionally managed soils is likely due to the accumulation of
18 304 soluble salts introduced through repeated applications of chemical fertilizers, increasing the
19 305 ionic strength of the soil solution. Whereas, organic carbon content in soil was found to be
20 306 higher and significantly different between the organic and conventional conditions. The direct
21 307 incorporation of these organic materials in the soil results in an enhancement of the organic
22 308 carbon content of the soil. Further, the highest value of available macronutrients and
23 309 micronutrients was observed under organic soil (Table 1), which was statistically superior to
24 310 conventional soil (Van Diepeningen et al., 2006). The organic soil was reported to have higher
25 311 urease activity than the soil under conventional conditions. The process of ammonization,
26 312 ammonification, and mineralisation brought about by microbial-mediated enzyme systems is
27 313 active in organic amendments, thus contributing more soluble N. The increase in the availability
28 314 of potassium through the addition of organic sources may also be due to the decomposition of
29 315 organic matter, which releases significant amounts of CO₂ when dissolved in water, forms
30 316 carbonic acid, and can break down primary minerals and release nutrients (Mithlesh et al.,
31 317 2019).
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52 318 In terms of microbial abundance, the organic soil exhibited a significantly higher bacterial load,
53 319 actinobacteria, and fungal colonies. These findings align perfectly with previous studies by
54 320 Shannon et al. (2002) and Banding et al. (2004). A comparison between conventional and
55 321 organic soil management practices revealed important differences in microbial communities,
56 322 with higher ATP concentrations and a greater abundance of fungi in organically managed soils.
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323 However, the impact of management strategies on total bacterial counts was indiscernible, as
324 reported by Crecchio et al. (2004). The observed variations in microbial biomass between the
325 two soil types are consistent with the differences measured in this study. Specifically, the lower
326 microbial activity and reduced AWCD values recorded in the conventional soil, compared to
327 the organic soil, indicate a decline in microbial functional capacity under conventional
328 management. This pattern is further supported by the lower diversity indices observed in the
329 conventional treatment. These results suggest that repeated applications of inorganic fertilizers
330 may influence microbial activity and associated enzyme functions involved in nutrient cycling
331 (Dick, 1992). Overall, the findings of this study demonstrate that excessive use of chemical
332 inputs and fertilization practices are closely associated with measurable changes in microbial
333 community structure and function. Additionally, the indiscriminate and long-term use of
334 pesticides has been found to have detrimental effects on soil ecology, leading to alterations or
335 even the depletion of beneficial soil microflora that contribute to plant health (Kalia & Gosal,
336 2011; Savci, 2012). Moreover, the application of pesticides has been linked to a reduction in
337 the activities of soil enzymes, which serve as crucial indicators of soil health. This reduction
338 further diminishes the biological potential of conventionally managed soils to efficiently cycle
339 and mineralize organic nutrient sources (Dick, 1992; Hussain et al., 2009).

340 According to the enzymatic activity, phosphatase, β -galactosidase, and urease show higher
341 activity levels in organic soil compared to conventional soil. This finding aligns with previous
342 studies that have demonstrated the significant influence of soil management techniques, such
343 as conventional versus organic management, on the activity of important soil enzymes. For
344 instance, a study conducted by Smith et al. (2005) found that soil management practices and
345 land use had a notable impact on the activities of urease, phosphodiesterase, arylsulphatase, and
346 β -glucosidase.

347 In line with these findings, Bandick & Dick, (1999) observed that continuous grass fields
348 exhibited higher enzyme activities compared to cultivated fields, and this activity was further
349 enhanced by the addition of cover crops or organic residues. These results suggest that enzyme
350 activity can be enhanced through biological management practices, which often involve the
351 utilization of organic fertilizers and cover crops. Additionally, Sharma et al. (2013)
352 demonstrated that optimal water supply and conservation tillage practices can also increase
353 enzyme activity, indicating that these techniques have the potential to further augment the
354 benefits of biological management.

355 The higher enzymatic activity observed in organic soil can be attributed to the presence of
1 356 organic inputs and improved soil conservation practices. Organic fertilizers and cover crops
2 357 provide a source of organic matter, which serves as a substrate for microbial activity and
3 358 enzyme production. These practices promote a more diverse and active microbial community,
4 359 leading to increased enzymatic activity in the soil. The structure and function of the soil
5 360 microbial community are commonly used as indicators of soil quality and fertility (Schloter et
6 361 al., 2018). The utilization of the carbonaceous substrate, assessed through Biolog EcoPlates,
7 362 revealed that the agricultural system relying on the addition of conventional chemical inputs
8 363 altered the metabolic potential of the microbial community, and this effect was highly
9 364 pronounced.

10 365 This study examines the effect of long-term agricultural practices on community-level
11 366 physiological profiles (CLPP) and soil enzymatic activities in tomato-cultivated soils. The
12 367 CLPP results revealed clear differences in microbial functional diversity between organic and
13 368 conventional systems (Choudhary et al., 2023), as reflected by higher average well color
14 369 development (AWCD), substrate richness, and Shannon–Weaver index in organically managed
15 370 soils (Wolińska et al., 2017). These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting
16 371 enhanced carbon utilization potential in organic systems (Choudhary et al., 2023; Wolińska et
17 372 al., 2017). Similarly, Islam et al. (2011) demonstrated that the combined application of compost
18 373 and chemical fertilizers significantly increased functional diversity compared to chemical
19 374 fertilization alone or untreated soils (Islam et al., 2011). A study by Chavarria et al. (2018) also
20 375 reported that agroecological management promotes greater microbial growth and metabolic
21 376 efficiency, leading to more effective carbon substrate utilization.

22 377 The substrate-level analysis further supports these observations. The heatmap (Figure 4)
23 378 highlights distinct patterns of carbon source utilization between the two soil management
24 379 systems, indicating that microbial communities respond differently to available substrates.
25 380 Organic soil exhibited greater variability and intensity of substrate consumption, suggesting a
26 381 broader functional capacity. This variability likely reflects differences in resource availability
27 382 and microbial community composition. This aligned perfectly with the findings by Arcand et
28 383 al. (2017), who showed that organically managed soils harbor structurally and functionally
29 384 distinct microbial communities due to variations in nutrient inputs and agronomic practices. In
30 385 addition, soil characteristics and organic matter composition play key roles in shaping microbial
31 386 activity and carbon utilization dynamics, ultimately influencing carbon cycling and storage
32 387 (Sävström et al., 2016).

388 5 Conclusion

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3 389 This study evaluated differences in the functional diversity and structure of soil microbial
4 390 communities under two tomato production systems in Morocco: conventional and
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6 391 agroecological. The results demonstrated that microbial communities are highly sensitive to
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8 392 management practices. Conventional soil exhibited lower microbial biomass, enzymatic
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10 393 activities, and metabolic capacity, indicating reduced microbial diversity and soil biochemical
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12 394 quality compared to agroecological soil.

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15 395 Overall, agroecological management was associated with enhanced microbial diversity and
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17 396 functional potential, highlighting its importance for maintaining soil health and supporting
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19 397 sustainable agricultural productivity. These findings underscore the role of soil enzymatic
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21 398 activity as a key indicator of microbial functionality. From an applied perspective, promoting
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23 399 agroecological practices such as the use of organic amendments and reduced reliance on
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25 400 synthetic inputs can improve nutrient cycling, enhance soil fertility, and increase system
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27 401 resilience to environmental stress. Such practices offer practical strategies for sustainable soil
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29 402 management and long-term productivity in tomato-based systems. Further research is needed
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31 403 to better understand the mechanisms underlying these differences and their long-term
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33 404 implications for soil ecosystem functioning.

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37 406 CRediT authorship contribution statement

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40 407 Khawla Bouamri: Writing review & editing, Writing original draft, Visualization, Validation,
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42 408 Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation,
43
44 409 Conceptualization. Hicham Oukfi: Visualization, Software, Writing original draft. Ilham
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46 410 Zouitane: Resources, Investigation. Said Louahlia: Supervision, Conceptualization, Validation,
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48 411 Investigation. Rachid Bouamri: Methodology, Visualization, Validation. Khalid Derraz:
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50 412 Validation, Investigation. Saad IBNSOUDA: Validation, Resources. Naïma El Ghachtouli:
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52 413 Writing review & editing, Writing original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision,
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54 414 Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data
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56 415 curation, Conceptualization.

57 416 Funding

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417 This research was supported by the PRIMA initiative (Partnership for Research and Innovation
1 418 in the Mediterranean Area) within the framework of the ASTER project “Strategies and tools
2 419 inspired by agroecology to improve resilience and ecosystem services in tomato cultivation,”
3 420 which is funded by the Department of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Morocco.
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7 421 **Declaration of competing interest**

10 422 There are no conflicts of interest regarding this publication declared by the authors.
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15 424 **Acknowledgements**

18 425 The authors thank all members of the Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology and Bioactive
19 426 Molecules for their material support, which significantly aided this study.
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546 **Figures captions**1
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547 **Figure 1:** Urease activity (A), β -galactosidase activity (B), and Phosphatase activity (C)
548 measured in organic (Org) and conventional (Conv) soil. Values indicate the average of n=3.
549 For each soil, different letters denote significant differences among methods following the
550 Tukey test ($p < 0.05$).

551 **Figure 2:** Kinetics of Average well color development (AWCD) of microbial communities in
552 organic and conventional soil over time, 180h.

553 **Figure 3:** (A) Comparison of carbon source utilization between conventional and organic soil
554 based on substrate type. Each value is the mean of three repetitions \pm SE (***: significant
555 difference). (B) Evenness, Richness, and Shannon index of conventional and organic soil.

556 **Figure 4:** Heatmap showing the differences in carbon utilization between conventional and
557 organic soils for the substrates in the Biolog EcoPlates.

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560 **Tables**561 **Table 1:** Physicochemical parameters of organic and conventional soil.

Soil	P (mg/Kg)	N-NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/Kg)	N-NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/Kg)	K (mg/Kg)	Mg (mg/Kg)	Ca (mg/Kg)	Mn (mg/Kg)	Fe (mg/Kg)
Organic	10.1±1.1	11±0.9	10.1±0.7	46±3.1	27±2.4	94±5.6	19.8±2.8	28.9±3.1
Conventional	12.1±2.1	7.9±0.5	3.6±0.5	39.8±2.3	19.9±2.2	51±4.1	3.05±0.4	20.06±2.3

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563 **Table 2:** Enumeration of microorganisms in different culture media: Luria-Bertani (LB), TCA,
564 Malt extract (MA). Values indicate the average of n=3. For each soil, different letters denote
565 significant differences among methods following the Tukey test ($p < 0.05$).

Microorganisms	Conventional soil	Organic soil
Bacteria (CFU 10⁶ g⁻¹of soil)	145.66 ±9 b	230 ±17.7 a
Actinomycetes (CFU 10⁶ g⁻¹of soil)	13.33 ±5.7 b	73.33 ±5.7 a
Fungi (CFU10⁶ g⁻¹of soil)	0.5 ±0.001 b	3.6 ±0.5 a

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582 **Figure 2:** Kinetics of Average well color development (AWCD) of microbial communities in
583 organic and conventional soil over time, 180h.

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585 (A)

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(B)

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589 **Figure 3:** (A) Comparison of carbon source
 590 utilization between conventional and organic
 591 soil based on substrate type. Each value is the
 592 mean of three repetitions \pm SE (***: significant
 593 difference). (B) Evenness, Richness, and
 594 Shannon index of conventional and organic
 595 soil.

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Figure 4: Heatmap showing the differences in carbon utilization between conventional and organic soils for the substrates in the Biolog EcoPlates.

Highlights

- ❖ Agroecological practices enhance soil fertility in tomato cultivation
- ❖ Organic system boosts metabolic activity and functional diversity
- ❖ Conventional system degrades microbial diversity and activity

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Declaration of interests

- ✓ The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.
- ✓ The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.